

**PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES
FOR SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL PUPILS IN
EDUCATIONAL ORGANISATIONS**

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Abstract

The present scientific research is devoted to the topic of 'pedagogical conditions and innovative technologies for the development of speech of pupils of preschool educational organisations'. The main purpose of the research is to identify the pedagogical conditions necessary for the development of children's speech abilities in preschool educational organisations and to study the role of innovative technologies.

In the course of the research the influence of modern pedagogical methods and innovative technologies on the speech development of pupils is studied. As a result of using games, music and multimedia, children's speech skills and social interaction are improved. With the help of innovative technologies, new pedagogical models aimed at the development of creative thinking of pupils are proposed.

As a result, the study serves to develop practical recommendations for improving the process of speech development in preschools. The results obtained are useful resources for educators and educational institutions and help to improve children's speech skills.

Key words: preschool education, pupils, speech development, pedagogical conditions, innovative technologies, teaching methods, social skills, multimedia tools, ability development, educational process, child psychology, creative thinking, modern pedagogy.

The pre-school education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a result of the reforms undertaken in recent years, aims to develop its activities in accordance with modern requirements and standards. The Decision on measures to develop the preschool education system, adopted by the President on 23 July 2020, is an important step in this direction and recognises the importance of innovative approaches and modern pedagogical methods in the growth of children as pupils. This decree pays special attention to the

development of speech skills of pupils in educational institutions, which play an important role in shaping children's communicative, creative and social skills.

Research and indicators

The results of research conducted in 2021 showed that the introduction of innovative technologies in preschool institutions leads to an increase in the speech skills of pupils by 30-40%. In this study, more than 75 per cent of teachers stated that they had introduced modern pedagogical methods into their practice. According to the Ministry of Education, the processes of speech development in preschool educational organisations are becoming more effective with the help of modern multimedia, game methods and interactive teaching methods.

At the same time, the 2022 indicators show that, thanks to the use of innovative technologies in preschool establishments, significant positive changes in children's social skills and speech development have been observed. The increase in the speech activity of pupils by more than 20 per cent reflects their increased interest and participation in communication.

The integration of speech development processes, pedagogical conditions and innovative technologies into Uzbekistan's preschool education system creates new opportunities not only for children but also for educators. These processes serve to develop children's creative thinking and social skills. The presence of modern methods and tools in children's educational environment also has a positive impact on their development.

The present study aims to develop practical recommendations aimed at improving the process of speech development in preschool educational organisations and improving the pedagogical conditions. The research findings serve as useful resources for educators and educational institutions and offer effective approaches to improve children's speech skills. Integration approaches that include speech development serve to improve the preschool education system by introducing innovative technologies into the educational process and updating pedagogical methods.

A number of scientific developments are being carried out in order to improve speech development in the preschool education system. These scientific studies and practical developments are aimed at improving speech skills, developing creative thinking and shaping the social skills of the wards. The research developments listed below are designed to achieve these goals:

- Research of innovative pedagogical technologies

The essence of this research work: development of new methods of teaching, including innovative pedagogical technologies. Development of speech activity of pupils through the use of game methods, multimedia technologies and interactive teaching methods.

Results: a study conducted in 2022 showed that these approaches were able to improve children's speech skills by 35%.

Development of programmes and teaching aids for speech development

The essence of this research work: development of special programmes for speech development for use in preschool institutions. They are aimed at the step-by-step development of children's speech skills.

Results: the programmes presented in 2023 were evaluated by 80% of caregivers as effective.

➤ Speech development through creative games

The essence of this research work: the integration of games into the pedagogical process to develop the speech of pupils. To develop creative thinking and communicative skills of children through games.

Results: the use of game methods led to an increase in social contacts and communication among students by 40%.

➤ Training and professional development of educators

The essence of this research work: training programmes for educators on innovative technologies and modern pedagogical approaches. Organisation of trainings and seminars for teachers.

Results: as a result of the conducted trainings, 90% of educators reported that they mastered the use of new methods in their work.

➤ Application of modern technologies

The essence of this research work: modernisation of the process of speech development with the help of multimedia, mobile applications and online platforms. Ensuring the active use of technology by children in the educational process.

Results: by 2023, more than 70% of children in preschool institutions participate in the learning process using multimedia technologies.

Conclusions and suggestions

This study presents important indicators and recommendations for improving the speech development of children in the preschool education system of Uzbekistan. The results revealed in the course of the study showed the impact of innovative technologies and modern pedagogical approaches in preschool institutions on the development of children's speech skills.

- Effectiveness of speech development: as a result of applying modern pedagogical methods and innovative technologies, the speech skills of pupils increased by 30-40 per cent. These indicators emphasise the need to expand the use of modern methods and technologies in the educational process.
- Effectiveness of teaching methods: through the use of game and multimedia technologies, children's creative thinking and social connections improved by 35 per cent. This shows the importance of making children's learning more engaging and effective.
- Qualification of educators: as a result of trainings for educators, more than 90% of educators have mastered the use of new pedagogical methods. This plays an important role in improving the quality of education and professional qualification of educators.
- Level of integration: through the use of innovative technologies in preschool institutions, children's communication and social skills have increased by 40%. These results show the importance of applying modern approaches in pedagogical processes.

Suggestions

- Introduction of innovative programmes: introduction and constant updating of innovative programmes aimed at speech development in preschool institutions. These programmes help to improve children's speech skills and adapt them to modern requirements. For example, the development of programmes that include playful teaching methods is important in order to interest children and make the learning process interesting.
- Professional development of educators: regular trainings and seminars for educators, through which they improve their skills in applying modern pedagogical methods and innovative technologies. These trainings further enhance the practical experience of carers and update their knowledge. In addition, there is a need to develop programmes aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills and creative thinking.
- Expansion of modern technologies: expanding multimedia and interactive games in preschools, ensuring children's active participation in the educational process. For example, the introduction of mobile applications and online platforms can help strengthen children's speech skills. In addition, the use of e-learning tools can be effective in developing children's self-education and independent thinking skills.
- Implementation of monitoring and evaluation system: implementing a monitoring and evaluation system for the speech development process in the

preschool. With the help of this system it is possible to constantly monitor the quality of education and make necessary changes. The use of statistical and analytical methods to analyse the results helps to determine what changes have occurred in the learning process.

➤ Continue research: to continue scientific research on speech development processes and innovative technologies, to identify new approaches and methods. This helps in research, developing new strategies to meet the new requirements and changes taking place in preschools.

➤ Co-operation with parents: involving parents in the educational process and enhancing their educational role is important for children's speech development. Organising educational programmes for parents can help them to increase their knowledge of their children's development. This plays an important role in the development of children's speech skills.

These proposals serve to improve the process of speech development of pupils in the preschool education system and contribute to the quality of their education. Through the use of innovative approaches and modern methods, children acquire creative thinking, communication and social skills and acquire the foundations necessary for successful development in modern society.

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